

The Challenge And Breakthrough Of Realizing Dynamic Balance Of High-Level Talent Flow In Local Colleges And Universities In China

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Abstract

Based on the research results of dynamic balance theory, human capital theory and Organizational Longevity Theory, a questionnaire survey was conducted among 472 local university high-level talents (LUHT) , this paper probes into the reasons and challenges of realizing the dynamic balance of high-level talent flow (LUHTF) in local colleges and universities, and advances some countermeasures. It is found that solving the LUHTF problem and ensuring the survival and development of local university organizations are the two major reasons for realizing the dynamic balance of high-level talent flow (HTF) , however, there are some challenges at the national, local and individual levels, which may even affect the development of the country, the stability of the society, the survival of university organizations and the realization of individual values. To solve these problems, the state needs to issue HTF policy in time, local colleges and universities adopt the form of "Internal training and external introduction" to acquire high-level talents, and actively optimize the allocation of high-level talents, the individual promotes the professional ethics accomplishment unceasingly, establishes the correct flow view.

Introduction

Shulz and Becker's theory of human capital tells us that human capital is a variety of productive knowledge, labor and management skills possessed by human beings, its task is to optimize the allocation of human resources in a planned way according to the strategic requirements of the development of the organization, to stimulate the enthusiasm and creativity of the staff through rational allocation, and to make their work more efficient, therefore, the organization obtains the maximum use value, improves the productivity and economic efficiency of the enterprise, and then promotes the development of the enterprise. The same is true of the task of human capital in the field of education. High-level talents are the core human capital in local colleges and universities, which is a kind of dynamic existence. To obtain the maximum value of LUHT, we need to realize it through the flow of human capital. Local colleges and universities should let competent people take the corresponding positions in the organization through HTF. Managers should screen talents and match posts in time, and make reasonable adjustments through screening and matching, finally, to realize the optimized allocation between people and posts, and promote the development of local colleges and universities. The identification and matching of talents can not be accomplished simply by the coordination of personnel within the organization, but also by the "Flow" of personnel among the organizations. Therefore, this study discusses the dynamic balance of China's LUHTF motivation, and according to the existing challenges, put forward relevant measures.

Literature review

Slichter (1919) first put forward the concept of "flow". Mobley, W.H. (1977) put forward the concept of "talent flow" on this basis, and defined talent flow as the behavior of talents changing service units under the guidance of their personal wishes. Later, Olof Ejeremo, Claudio Fassio, John K ä llstr ö m (2019) explored the influencing factors of talent mobility in colleges and universities using empirical research methods, and explored the correlation between mobility and job promotion. Veugelers, V. & Bouwel, L.V. (2015) also focused on analyzing the influencing factors of the flow of European scholars to the United States. Zhang Nan (2019) made a key analysis from the perspective of concept. She believed that high-level talents have more professional knowledge and strong professional talents, can shoulder the social responsibility and lead the development of the industry. They are scarce human resources in society. Silvia AppelL (2015) believed that national R&D investment would affect the flow of high-level talents. Ratcliffe, E. , And K. M, Korpela (2016) proposed that mobility behavior is related to the living environment, as well as the sense of belonging and identity. Zheng Dailiang (2018) believed that the problem of HTF disorder in colleges and universities was serious; Peng Xiufen (2020) discussed the disadvantages of HTF disorder and the countermeasures for reasonable flow based on the push-pull theory against the background of double first-class construction; Zhou Haifeng and Lou Jia (2021)

discussed the causes and mechanisms of HTF in colleges and universities based on the background of China's double first-class construction.

In recent years, the Chinese government has also been paying close attention to the issue of HTF. On January 25, 2017, the General Office of the Ministry of Education of China issued the Notice of the General Office of the Ministry of Education on Adhering to the Correct Orientation and Promoting the Rational and Orderly Flow of High level Talents in Colleges and Universities, which proposed that colleges and universities should adhere to the correct orientation of talent flow and take morality and talent cultivation as the fundamental task of HTF. On February 8, 2022, the Ministry of Education also put forward in the Work Points of the Ministry of Education in 2022: in order to comprehensively improve the ability of education services, "accelerate the training and introduction of high-level talents urgently needed by the country."

The dynamic balance of this study belongs to the dynamic balance of personnel in higher education management, that is, colleges and universities take measures to enable high-level talents with higher abilities to take charge of important posts in their organizations through "talent mobility", and finally achieve dynamic balance between people and posts through mobility (Zhang Xiuqiong, 2019). Only by allowing the free flow of university human resources between industries and regions can universities move forward in stability and development (Yin Xiaoqing, 2019). Therefore, this study proposes three major issues, namely, the motivation, challenges and measures for LUHTF to achieve dynamic balance.

Research findings

3.1 Motivation for China's LUHTF to achieve dynamic balance

The motivation for China's LUHTF to achieve dynamic balance is mainly manifested in two aspects.

3.1.1 Need to solve LUHTF problem

Through the collection of relevant research literature, it is found that in recent years, HTF in Chinese universities has seen some chaos, which requires effective governance (Xu Juan, Jia Yongtang, 2019).

Table 1 Statistical table of information on the willingness of high-level talents to flow in local colleges and universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion
Do you have the will to move to another unit?	Don't want to flow	36	7.63%
	Generally	134	28.39%
	Willingness to move	78	16.53%
	Prefer to flow	158	33.47%
	Want to flow very much	66	13.98%

Source: Compiled by this study

As shown in Table 1, from the perspective of mobility willingness, among the 472 respondents, it was found that 302 high-level talents in local colleges and universities had the mobility willingness, and the proportion was as high as 63.98%. This result also shows that there are still some drawbacks in the management of high-level talents in China's local colleges and universities, and some factors that can cause the willingness of high-level talents to flow. The emergence of the phenomenon of orderly flow, and through reform and rational allocation, make the flow of high-level talents in local colleges and universities achieve a dynamic balance, rather than an imbalance.

Table 2 Statistics of high-level talent flow experience in local colleges and universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion
Have you changed work units since you started working?	是	80	16.95%
	否	392	83.05%

Source: Compiled by this study

Table 3 Statistics of high-level talent flow frequency in local colleges and universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion
How many times have you changed work units?	zero	392	83.05%
	1-2 times	54	11.44%

3-4 times	26	5.51%
Five or more times	0	0%

Source: Compiled by this study

As shown in Table 2, only 16.95% of people with real mobility experience, compared with the global proportion of 37.80%, the proportion of mobile personnel is not high. From the perspective of flow frequency, the flow frequency is mostly concentrated in 1-2 times, as shown in Table 3, which is also lower than the global flow frequency. In today's education globalization, the frequency of high-level talent flow in China's local universities is relatively unreasonable, which shows that although high-level talents in China's local universities have a strong willingness to flow, when they really face the problem of flow, they are often due to various factors. And timid, lack of courage and creativity. However, the survival and development of local colleges and universities requires the promotion of more courageous and creative talents to achieve a dynamic balance of personnel in the organization. The Chinese government also needs to make timely adjustments according to the needs of national development to effectively control the base and frequency of the flow of high-level talents in local universities.

Table 4 Statistics of high-level talent flow types in local colleges and universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion	Effective ratio (Empty)
What is your flow type?	Intercollegiate flow	62	13.14%	77.50%
	An inter-bank flow	18	3.81%	22.50%
	(Empty)	392	83.05%	0%

Source: Compiled by this study

As shown in Table 4, in terms of mobility types, most of the high-level talents in local universities in China choose inter-school mobility, but 22.50% of them also choose inter-bank mobility. If inter-school mobility is more conducive to local colleges and universities to achieve a dynamic balance of personnel, then the flow of high-level talents in local colleges and universities to other industries also provides conditions for other organizations to achieve dynamic balance to some extent.

Table 5 Information statistical table of high-level talent flow level changes in local universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion	Effective ratio (Empty)
Compared with your previous work unit, how is your work unit classified according to "flow"?	Lower than original unit	6	1.27%	7.50%
	Same as the original unit	14	2.97%	17.50%
	Higher than original unit	42	8.9%	52.50%
	Does not belong to the same nature with the original unit, cannot judge	18	3.81%	22.50%
	(Empty)	392	83.05%	0%

Source: Compiled by this study

From the perspective of changes in the level of mobility, 52.50% of high-level talents in local colleges and universities have flowed to new units higher than the original unit level, as shown in Table 5. This change of mobility level may be a good thing for high-level talents in local universities, but for local colleges and universities at low levels and low "flow", it will cause a large loss of high-level talents, which is not conducive to the realization of high-level talents. The dynamic balance of organizational personnel is also not conducive to the long-term development of the organization.

Table 6 Information statistical table of high-level talent flow direction in local universities

Investigate subject	Options	Frequency	Proportion	Effective ratio (Empty)
What is the direction of your mobility	To the political centers	24	5.08%	30.00%
	To economically developed cities	22	4.66%	27.50%
	To the cultural and academic center city flow	14	2.97%	17.50%

relative to your previous employer's location?	Flows to areas similar to the original geographic location	16	3.39%	20.00%
	Flow to an area inferior to its original geographical location	4	0.85%	5%
	(Empty)	392	83.05%	0%

Source: Compiled by this study

In terms of the flow direction, 75% of the high-level floating personnel in local colleges and universities flow to the political, economic, cultural and academic center cities, as shown in Table 6. Zhou Haifeng and Lou Jia (2019) pointed out that from the perspective of regional flow direction, most LUHT flows from relatively poor regions to relatively rich regions, from less developed cities to more developed cities, and from the middle and northwest to the southeast, starting the flow trend of "peacocks fly southeast". This phenomenon will cause imbalance in the proportion of regional talents, higher education resources, and even national and regional development.

For this reason, the General Office of the Ministry of Education (2017) clearly proposed in the Notice of the General Office of the Ministry of Education on Adhering to the Correct Orientation and Promoting the Rational and orderly Flow of High level Talents in Colleges and Universities that we should look at talent competition from an international perspective, focus on the introduction of overseas high-level talents, and increase the emphasis on the development of high-level talents in colleges and universities in the western and northeastern regions, taking into account the actual situation, Eastern universities are not encouraged to use their own advantages to introduce talents from universities in the central and western regions and northeast regions. It can be seen that the country is actively responding to the problems in the direction of LUHTF, and trying to take effective measures to make reasonable adjustments.

According to the above analysis on the current situation and problems of LUHTF, if you want to solve these mobility problems, you must consider the problem of LUHTF achieving dynamic balance. Only by achieving dynamic balance, can local colleges and universities achieve balanced allocation of high-level talent resources through talent flow. The disorder and imbalance of talent flow is not conducive to organizational development, that is to say, only by realizing the dynamic balance of LUHTF, can local universities achieve healthy and sustainable development.

3.1.2 The need for the survival and development of local university organizations

Chester Barnard's organizational balance theory, known as the "father of modern management theory", focuses on how organizations survive and develop. He believes that the survival and development of an organization can not be separated from "balance". Balance is relative, not absolute, and achieving balance is not achieved overnight. Because the constituent factors and influencing factors inside and outside the organization are always changing, changes are prone to imbalance. That is to say, the balance achieved at a time is only relative balance, not stable. With the change of environmental factors inside and outside the organization, The balance achieved at one time will be constantly broken, which requires the organization to make new adjustments in time according to the new situation to achieve new balance. Therefore, organizational balance is generally a dynamic balance of the organization.

3.2 The challenge of LUHTF to achieve dynamic balance

3.2.1 Challenges at the national level

For the country, the unreasonable flow of LUHT will have a serious impact on the country, and even affect the implementation of the national development strategy layout, affect education equity and stimulate social conflicts.

In recent years, although China has issued a number of policy documents on talent mobility, controlling the regional layout of educational human resources as a whole, increasing the gradient of high-level talent allocation in central and northwest universities, and trying to change the unbalanced status of LUHTF, from the previous survey results, LUHT mobility still presents some unreasonable status. From the survey results of "personal mobility willingness", LUHT is more likely to flow to the economically, politically and academically developed central regions, while universities in developed regions will also use their advantages to obtain more high-level talents. On the contrary, regions with relatively backward development will lose a large number of LUHT, further increase the polarization of education, seriously affect the balance of the educational equity ecosystem, and stimulate deep-seated social conflicts.

3.2.2 Challenges at the level of local universities

Although many local colleges and universities have been making unremitting efforts to achieve dynamic balance in HTF, there are often many problems that are difficult to control in reality, even the decision-makers' understanding of the concept of dynamic balance is still not in place, and there are still many deficiencies in practice. These can not be solved quickly overnight, and local colleges and universities need to face challenges and make continuous exploration and efforts.

(1) Internal imbalance exists, and the endogenous force of high-level talents is insufficient

Although many local colleges and universities have taken various measures to cultivate or introduce a group of high-level talents, which has injected new strength into the survival and development of schools, due to various factors, this strength is still limited. Therefore, the imbalance within the organization still exists, which to a certain extent causes the lack of endogenous force of high-level talents.

First, the phenomenon of power "reproduction" is serious. The so-called "reproduction" of power here refers to "position" and "academic". Because local colleges and universities are subordinate to local governments and their contacts are relatively concentrated, some people use their power to "breed" positions and academics. Although many local colleges and universities are constantly taking measures to avoid this phenomenon of power "reproduction", "informal" organizations still exist, and relatives and acquaintances are often the main source of their accumulated contacts. When LUHT is unable to hold an important position suitable for him, it is difficult to give full play to his personal talents effectively, which will lead to strong dissatisfaction, blocked work enthusiasm, and job burnout after a long time, resulting in insufficient endogenous strength of high-level talents. The same is true in the academic field. It has been a long time since papers are difficult to be published and topics are difficult to apply. For topics, many local topics adopt the method of "limited items" to apply. Once the items are limited, the phenomenon of power "reproduction" will occur. Some projects will flow into the name of "related households", and the success rate of high-level talents' application will be greatly reduced. In the long run, the job satisfaction of high-level talents will be reduced, The initiative of self growth and promotion will also decrease, even resulting in stress and anxiety, and the internal motivation of individuals will continue to decrease.

Secondly, there is a lack of high-level talent elimination mechanism. For local colleges and universities, the flow of high-level talents is composed of two aspects: outflow and inflow. Inflow is often positive and active, while outflow is active and passive. The active outflow of high-level talents is the voluntary resignation of high-level talents, while the passive outflow is the dismissal of high-level talents according to talent management policies. At present, the vast majority of LUHT in local colleges and universities leave their own units in the form of voluntary resignation, and only a few of them are dismissed by local colleges and universities due to serious problems of teachers' ethics and style. In fact, many local colleges and universities have not formulated relevant high-level talent elimination mechanisms, resulting in some so-called "high-level talents" taking the high salaries provided by local colleges and universities to "provide for the elderly". The lack of elimination mechanism will also cause the problem of insufficient endogenous power of LUHT, which will lead to the emergence of imbalance within the organization.

(2) Serious external imbalance and lack of core talents

External imbalance refers to the HTF imbalance between universities at the macro level. At present, LUHT mainly flows to developed regions and political academic centers, where high-level talents are gathered, while high-level talents in underdeveloped and poor regions are largely drained, which causes the external imbalance of LUHTF. Serious external imbalance will lead to the lack of core talents in the posts of backward local universities, which is also very unfavorable for local universities.

3.2.3 Personal challenges

Unreasonable mobility is often caused by individual irrational choice, which is also related to individual values and personal pursuit. Some LUHTs only use the "hat" as a springboard, completely disregarding their own professional ethics, and change jobs at will in order to seek temporary interests. They move freely, even leave without permission. This frequent flow will often reduce the stability of personal academic. Due to lack of concentration on scientific research, it will also reduce the quality and output of academic, seriously affect the exertion of personal ability, and is not conducive to the realization of personal value.

3.3 LUHTF to achieve dynamic balance breakthrough

LUHT is responsible for educating people for the country and the Party. Their mobility is related to the development of the country, the balance and stability of society, the survival and development of university organizations, and the realization of personal values. Therefore, it is of great practical significance to explore LUHTF's measures to achieve dynamic balance.

3.3.1 Strengthen national policy guidance and promote the reform of high-level talent development system and mechanism

Paul Samuelson once proposed that the mixed economy needs the government to introduce relevant policies to correct the challenges caused by the defects of the market economy (Gao Xiaoyong and Wang Dingding, 2005). The flow of LUHT is closely related to the allocation of market resources, and the government also needs to issue corresponding policies to guide it. The reality is that the introduction of policies often has two sides, as stated in the public choice theory: the good side is self-evident, which can provide reasonable guidance, but imperfect policies may also make the situation worse (Randy T. Simmons, 2017).

In view of this, the researchers believe that LUHTF policy should be based on scientific and reasonable basis, comprehensively consider the actual situation of the country, organizations and individuals, put forward scientific and reasonable countermeasures, constantly reform and innovate the evaluation mechanism, and establish a reasonable talent flow mechanism.

3.3.2 Local universities should improve mobility strategies and optimize the allocation of high-level talents

Kaz's tissue life theory enlightens us that LUHT needs to maintain the vitality of the organization through mobility, and LUHTF is to break the rigid static balance, so that the organization can maintain its vitality, survival and development in the dynamic balance. In this context, local colleges and universities need to pay attention to the dynamic balance of HTF, and constantly take measures to achieve this dynamic balance.

(1) "Internal training and external introduction": multiple measures are taken to obtain high-level talents

If LUHTF wants to achieve balance, it needs to take various methods to acquire talents. Among them, "internal training and external introduction" is an important way, which is also an effective way to solve the internal imbalance of local colleges and universities, the serious internal and external imbalance of high-level talents, and the lack of core post talents.

The so-called "internal training" is to cultivate high-level talents internally. The best way is to improve the qualifications of teachers in local colleges and universities, and promote teachers to move towards the goal of high-level talents. Local colleges and universities can encourage their teachers to read doctor's degrees or go abroad to study. For teachers in local colleges and universities, reading doctor's degrees or visiting students is conducive to rapidly improving teachers' scientific research ability and stimulating their enthusiasm for scientific research. When teachers' scientific research ability becomes stronger and stronger, they will produce some academically outstanding high-level talents, which is also a major way to obtain high-level talents.

The so-called "external introduction" is to recruit talents from other universities or fields to attract high-level talents. Under the background of the era strategy of "making the country strong through science and technology" and "making the country strong through talents", all sectors of society appear to be crazy about attracting talents, especially eager to seize high-level talents. In order to achieve the dynamic balance of HTF in local colleges and universities, local colleges and universities also need to deal with the shortage or poaching of high-level talents through "external introduction", which is also an effective way to effectively solve the serious external imbalance of local colleges and universities and the lack of core talents.

(2) Optimize the allocation of high-level talents

For local colleges and universities, the construction of teachers plays an important role, which can effectively promote the development of local colleges and universities. When local colleges and universities have a complete set of talent team construction plans that are suitable for the nature of colleges and universities, colleges and universities have huge talent potential, but only potential is not enough. Colleges and universities should also take positive measures to constantly optimize the allocation of teachers, especially high-level talent team, and always guard against the unreasonable problem of LUHT team configuration, so that the ability of high-level talents can be fully played.

The allocation of teachers should mainly focus on the following aspects: first, the gender allocation of teachers, second, the age structure of teachers, and third, the proportion of teachers' qualifications and professional titles. Gender collocation can effectively stimulate the follow-up development vitality of local colleges and universities, age structure can effectively guarantee the future development potential of local colleges and universities, and the proportion of teachers' qualifications and professional titles can effectively guarantee the overall quality of teachers in local colleges and universities. Only a reasonable allocation of teachers can make local colleges and universities achieve sustainable and stable development.

4.3.3 Improve professional ethics and establish a correct concept of mobility

LUHT is a kind of high-end group integrating knowledge and culture. It is not only responsible for preaching, imparting and solving doubts, but also for shaping students' character. It is an important guide on students' life. Therefore, we should pay more attention to personal professional ethics, establish a correct concept of mobility, constantly improve ourselves and forge ahead.

In a word, local colleges and universities have improved the insufficient number of high-level talents, internal imbalance and external imbalance through "internal training and external introduction".

Conclusion

To solve the LUHTF problem, we need to adopt a dynamic balance strategy. The survival and development of local university organizations also need to achieve a dynamic balance of the organization. However, the reality is that many LUHTFs still face certain challenges in the process of achieving dynamic balance. For example, unreasonable mobility affects the implementation of national development strategy layout and education equity, and stimulates social conflicts; The internal imbalance of local colleges and universities exists, the endogenous force of high-level talents is insufficient, the external imbalance of the organization is serious, and the post core talents are missing; Personal ability is affected and personal value is difficult to realize. In response to the above challenges, local colleges and universities need to take effective measures in a timely manner to obtain high-level talents through policies issued by the state and diversified measures taken by the organization in the form of "internal training and external introduction", reasonably optimize the allocation of high-level talents, strengthen personal professional ethics and other ways to actively solve them, and help LUHTF achieve dynamic balance as soon as possible.

5. Research limitations and suggestions for future research

This study only discusses the issues related to the realization of dynamic balance of LUHTF in China. Local universities only refer to undergraduate colleges and higher vocational (junior college) colleges in ordinary universities, while Chinese universities also include central departments, adult colleges and private universities in ordinary universities. The reasons and problems for these different types of universities to achieve dynamic balance of HTF may be different, and the measures taken may also be different. Therefore, future research should focus on other relevant groups.

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